

On the friction and lubrication of 3D printed Ti6Al4V hip joint replacement

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1 ABSTRACT

2 The present study investigates the tribological performance of 3D printed Ti6Al4V total
3 hip replacements (THR) compared to conventionally produced THR from CoCrMo and
4 FeNiCr alloys. The objective was to evaluate the suitability of 3D printed titanium alloy, with
5 and without DLC coating, for THR rubbing surfaces and to investigate the potential benefits of
6 3D printing technology for friction and lubrication. A pendulum hip joint simulator was
7 employed to replicate the swinging motion of a hip joint, thereby enabling the measurements
8 of coefficient of friction (COF) and the observation of lubricant film formation under realistic

1 conditions between the metal femoral head and acetabular cup. The experiments demonstrated
2 that additive manufacturing enables the creation of specific surface topographies that can
3 enhance protein adsorption, but also introduce surface imperfections negatively affecting
4 tribological properties. The elevated surface roughness of additively manufactured femoral
5 heads did not inevitably result in an increase in COF and was comparable to that of
6 conventionally manufactured femoral heads. The additively manufactured Ti6Al4V head
7 without DLC coating also exhibited a more rapid increase in lubricant film thickness during
8 dynamic motion. In conclusion, the findings indicate that while 3D printing offers promising
9 advancements in implant customization and material properties, its application requires careful
10 consideration of surface finishing and coating methods to achieve optimal tribological
11 performance.

12 **KEYWORDS**

13 Total hip replacement, Ti6Al4V, DLC coating, Lubricant film formation, Friction

14 **1. INTRODUCTION**

15 Total hip arthroplasty (THA) represents a significant advancement in surgical
16 techniques, with millions of individuals reporting enhanced quality of life following the
17 procedure. A common indication for total hip replacement (THR) is a traumatic hip injury or
18 advanced arthritis of the hip. In such cases, the procedure has the potential to significantly
19 alleviate pain and restore mobility. Although THR has a high survival rate of approximately
20 77.6% at 25 years [1], it can occasionally fail at an earlier point in time [2], which presents a
21 specific risk for younger patients. For patients aged between 50 and 54 years, the estimated
22 lifetime risk of THR revision is up to 29% [3]. Therefore, research focused on improving the
23 durability of THR remains crucial. The longevity of THR is influenced by a number of factors,
24 the majority of which relate to the implant/bone interaction, as well as the wear of the
25 articulating surfaces [4]. When identifying the main cause of implant failure, aseptic loosening
26 due to osteolysis is often recognised as a primary cause [5]. Loosening results from wear

1 particles released from the rubbing surfaces during joint articulation, emphasising the critical
2 role of biotribology in improving implant durability [6]. The wear of articulating surfaces is
3 closely related to the materials of rubbing surfaces.

4 One of the most widely used groups of materials for THR rubbing surfaces is metal
5 alloys, including stainless steel and CoCrMo. Metal femoral heads or acetabular cups are
6 conventionally manufactured by casting and polishing. However, additive manufacturing (AM)
7 of CoCrMo or titanium alloys represents a progressive method of production, offering
8 numerous potential advantages for THR development. An important focus in additively
9 manufactured THR research is understanding the changes in lubrication, friction, and wear
10 processes in comparison with conventionally produced THR, as these factors could
11 significantly impact the performance and lifespan of the implants. Addressing these challenges
12 through an enhanced understanding of lubrication performance is essential, as insufficient
13 lubrication leads to increased friction and an elevated wear rate, which ultimately determines
14 the lifespan of implant.

15 Mavraki and Cann [7] were the first to use optical interferometry to measure lubricant
16 film thickness, simplifying THR conditions into a ball-on-disc setup (steel ball and glass disc).
17 They found that the film thickness increased with motion speed for bovine serum (BS), whereas
18 a synthetic protein solution mimicking synovial fluid (SF) showed a more constant film
19 thickness across varying speeds. Subsequent research [8] examined the effects of pressure and
20 temperature, revealing that film thickness rapidly decreased under sliding conditions as proteins
21 were wiped away. Fan et al. [9] replaced the stainless-steel ball with a CoCrMo femoral head
22 to study the effects of speed and lubricant composition under sliding conditions. A thin adhered
23 layer formed quickly, with the film thickness increasing due to hydrodynamic effects,
24 particularly at lower speeds. Myant et al. [10] adopted the same experimental configuration,
25 focusing on the behaviour of key SF proteins, such as albumin and γ -globulin. Static-load

1 experiments showed that γ -globulin formed a more substantial adsorbed layer, while albumin
2 created only a thin layer unaffected by protein concentration. In dynamic tests, both proteins
3 formed agglomerations that periodically increased the film thickness.

4 The importance of replicating realistic joint movement was later confirmed in studies
5 by Myant et al. [11], who found that transitioning from unidirectional to reversal motion, better
6 mimicking the joint function caused a significant reduction in the lubricant film thickness. The
7 knowledge was summarized in the upcoming study, which presented multiple aspects of the so-
8 called protein aggregation lubrication (PAL) regime, highlighting the main differences against
9 classical elastohydrodynamic lubrication (EHL) theory [12]. To address the issue of surface
10 conformity and contact pressure, Vrbka et al. [13] modified the experimental ball-on-disc setup
11 by a concave glass lens. This adjustment enabled a more accurate representation of lubricant
12 behaviour, showing that conformal contact led to a thicker and more stable lubricant film. To
13 further enhance the importance of contact conformity, the authors later developed a pendulum-
14 based simulator that replicated the actual contact arrangement of a hip joint, introducing a ball-
15 in-cup configuration suitable for in-situ contact observation [14]. The findings confirmed that
16 smaller implants promoted thicker lubricant films, and lower clearances significantly improved
17 lubrication performance [15].

18 In later studies, Nečas et al. [16] compared BS with model SFs containing albumin, γ -
19 globulin, hyaluronic acid (HA), and phospholipids in concentrations mimicking healthy and
20 pathological SF. It was revealed that the composition and interaction of SF constituents are
21 critical for lubrication, with HA playing a vital role in film formation. To further investigate the
22 role of individual SF constituents within THR lubrication, Nečas et al. [4] developed
23 methodology based on fluorescent microscopy to focus on the performance of stained albumin
24 and γ -globulin. Their experiments revealed that γ -globulin formed a thin, stable layer, while
25 albumin contributed to film enhancement. Further research explored the differences in

1 lubrication mechanisms in hard-on-soft and hard-on-hard implant pairs. Various lubricants
2 were tested, revealing that γ -globulin, HA, and phospholipids interact to form a thin boundary
3 layer, which allows albumin to layer on top [17]. In hard pairs, the lubricant film tended to thin,
4 while using poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) cups increased film thickness, aligning with
5 previous findings on the sensitivity of SF films to contact pressure. Despite having thicker films,
6 soft pairs showed higher friction, suggesting that internal friction within the lubricant film plays
7 a significant role [18].

8 AM represents a progressive method of production across a wide range of applications,
9 and is also being integrated into the manufacturing process of joint implants [19]. Currently,
10 3D printing is most commonly utilized in the fabrication of prostheses for the reconstruction of
11 bone segments or entire bones affected by injury, osteomyelitis-induced defects [19], or tumour
12 resection [20]. Moreover, the manufacturing process allows for the creation of a structured
13 implant surface, which facilitates enhanced bone ingrowth, maturation and fixation stability
14 [21].

15 One of the biocompatible materials suitable for 3D printing is titanium alloy Ti6Al4V.
16 The majority of publications on 3D printed Ti6Al4V alloy have primarily focused on sections
17 of the joint replacements that do not form rubbing surfaces. Nevertheless, a number of studies
18 have initiated this research, offering preliminary insights into this field of investigation. In a
19 study conducted by Grosse et al. [22], a comparison was made between the wear characteristics
20 of CoCr and titanium alloys produced through conventional manufacturing (CM) processes.
21 The findings indicated that the titanium alloy exhibited wear levels that were up to double those
22 observed in the CoCr alloy. Similarly, Odehnal et al. [23] observed comparable results, noting
23 that the Ti6Al4V alloy exhibited significantly higher wear accompanied by the formation of
24 deep grooves. Moreover, the formation of the lubricating film was investigated, and it was
25 found that the Ti6Al4V alloy demonstrated inferior lubricating properties in comparison to the

1 CoCrMo alloy. Other studies have employed experimental methods to compare the properties
2 of AM and CM titanium alloys. A comparison of the percentage of α and β phases reveals
3 significant discrepancies [24] in the relative proportions of these phases. In the case of the CM
4 alloy, the alpha phase represents a mere 25% of the total composition, whereas in the AM alloy,
5 this proportion rises to 75%. Goyal et al. [25] and Bartolomeu et al. [24] conducted experiments
6 in ball-on-disk configuration to compare AM and CM titanium alloys in contact with an Al_2O_3
7 ball and simulated body fluid (SBF), respectively, with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) as a
8 lubricant. The findings showed that, regardless of the applied load, a reduction in wear was
9 consistently observed for the AM alloy. This is attributed to the presence of harder
10 microstructural constituents, which are formed during production through the utilization of a
11 high cooling rate. Moreover, Goyal's [25] experiments demonstrated a reduction in the
12 coefficient of friction (CF) for all forces. In contrast, Bartolomeu [24] reported that a notable
13 difference in friction was not apparent.

14 Although it has been demonstrated that the use of AM has resulted in enhanced wear
15 characteristics, there is still a lack of comprehensive characterization of the tribological
16 behavior of the AM titanium alloy in the frictional contact. It may therefore be necessary to
17 employ a coating in order to optimize the performance of the alloy. Diamond-like carbon (DLC)
18 is the most prevalent coating material used for articular implants, which offers a crucial benefit
19 of reducing the wear rate. However, the DLC coating can also have a negative impact on the
20 human body, particularly in terms of the delamination [26] that can occur. Consequently, efforts
21 have been made to identify an appropriate interlayer [27], [28] or finishing operation to be
22 applied to the substrate material [29] in order to enhance its behaviour and prevent potential
23 issues.

24 The lubrication of THR is a complex process, the outcome of which is influenced by a
25 number of factors. These include the material used for the femoral head and acetabular cup,

1 implant geometry, surface conformity, SF composition, motion dynamics, and so forth. The
2 ongoing research in this area is contributing to a refinement of our understanding of lubrication
3 processes, which may identify potential areas for improvement in future THRs. The advent of
4 additive manufacturing technologies gives rise to novel research questions, particularly in the
5 context of 3D printing of biocompatible materials such as the Ti6Al4V alloy. It prompts the
6 inquiry of whether a 3D printed femoral head can serve as a rubbing surface for a THR. It is
7 therefore pertinent to ask whether the tribological properties of a 3D printed Ti6Al4V femoral
8 head are comparable to those of conventionally manufactured THRs made from stainless steel
9 or CoCrMo alloys. In addition, it is worth investigating whether its tribological behaviour can
10 be improved in any way, for example, by applying a coating to the rubbing surfaces. In order
11 to respond to these questions, the present study aims to conduct a comprehensive tribological
12 assessment of a conventionally produced metal femoral heads and a 3D printed Ti6Al4V
13 femoral heads with or without a DLC coating in a realistic ball-in-cup configuration. The
14 pendulum hip joint simulator, together with the optical interferometry and fluorescent
15 microscopy apparatus, will be utilised to analyse the COF and lubricant film formation in the
16 contact between the CoCrMo, FeNiCr or Ti6Al4V femoral heads and the ultra-high-molecular-
17 weight polyethylene (UHMWPE), PMMA or glass acetabular cup.

18 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

19 **2.1. Experimental setup**

20 In order to replicate the swinging motion of a hip joint, a pendulum hip joint simulator
21 (Fig. 1) was utilized to conduct frictional measurements and observations of lubricant film
22 formation. The simulator comprises a static frame that holds a pot with an acetabular cup fixed
23 with a resin, and a movable frame (pendulum). The femoral head is attached to the movable
24 frame, which applies a load on the femoral head and enables the swinging motion between the
25 femoral head and the acetabular cup. The range of swinging motion is limited by the simulator

1 design and is $\pm 16^\circ$, which corresponds to the range of flexion-extension motion in a human hip.
2 The frequency of the swinging motion is approximately 0.5 Hz, which is closely comparable to
3 the slow pace of gait observed in elderly people.

4 In order to observe the formation of the lubricant film, two distinct optical techniques
5 were utilized. The first method, fluorescence microscopy, permits the separation and
6 observation of individual constituents of SF (albumin, γ -globulin, HA), so their role in lubricant
7 film formation can be clarified. The principle of fluorescence phenomena involves three stages.
8 Initially, photons are excited by the light source and subsequently absorbed by the fluorescent
9 dye within the tested lubricant. This phase is called excited-state lifetime, lasts 1-10 ns, while
10 the molecule undergoes relaxation. This results in partial energy dissipation, which enhances
11 the fluorescence emission. Consequently, the emitted photons have lower energy, causing the
12 emitted radiation to have a longer wavelength than the excited radiation. This shift allows for
13 the separation of excitation and emission, enabling the determination of the fluorescence yield.

14 For fluorescence measurements, the pendulum simulator was enhanced with the
15 incorporation of a bespoke microscope, as illustrated schematically in Fig. 1 (left). The contact
16 area was illuminated by a light-emitting diode, and the light passed through a set of optical
17 filters to achieve the required wavelength of emitted and excited light. The data obtained from
18 the in-situ observations were recorded with a high-speed complementary metal-oxide
19 semiconductor (CMOS) camera, the Andor Neo 5.5 (Andor, Belfast, UK). As a counter surface
20 to the metal femoral heads, a transparent PMMA acetabular cup was used. PMMA was selected
21 for its transparency and to mimic the mechanical properties of the UHMWPE acetabular cup, a
22 commonly used material in orthopaedics. The functionality of the apparatus had already been
23 validated and described in more detail in a previous publication by Nečas et al. [17].

1
2 **Fig. 1** Experimental apparatus

3 To obtain specific information about lubricant film thickness, a fluorescence
4 microscope was replaced with an optical interferometry apparatus (Fig. 1 (right)). This
5 configuration comprised a high-speed digital camera Phantom v710 (Vision Research, Wayne,
6 NJ, USA), an optical microscope, and a light source. The apparatus has been validated and
7 described in detail in previous studies [14], [15]. The PMMA acetabular cup was replaced by a
8 BK7 glass cup, which was coated with an anti-reflective layer on the bottom and a semi-
9 reflective chromium layer on the frictional surface to enhance the contrast of interference
10 fringes. The glass cup was selected for its transparency and suitability for achieving optimal
11 coating adhesion.

12 **2.2. Materials**

13 Femoral heads, machined in both additive and conventional ways, were tested.
14 Conventional methods, namely casting and polishing, were employed to produce CoCrMo
15 (ASTM-F75) and FeNiCr (ISO 5832-1) alloy samples. Ti6Al4V (ISO 5832-3) samples, with or
16 without a DLC coating, were manufactured using the SLM 3D printing method, followed by
17 conventional surface finishing. All femoral heads were produced by ProSpon (Kladno,
18 Czechia), certified producer of Ti6Al4V 3D printed bone implants and joint replacements. Prior
19 to the experiments, the geometry of all femoral heads was evaluated using an optical 3D
20 scanner, the ATOS Triple Scan (GOM, Braunschweig, Germany), in order to analyse the exact

1 diameter and to identify any deviations from an ideal spherical shape. The nominal diameter of
2 the femoral heads was 28 mm, whereas the 3D scanner measured a real diameter of a 27.98 mm
3 for all four femoral heads. The 3D scans of the femoral heads are presented in Fig. 2 (left
4 column).

5 Additionally, the surface topography of the samples was evaluated. The surface
6 roughness (S_a) was determined using a Bruker Contour GT-X8 optical profilometer (Bruker,
7 Billerica, MA, USA), which employs phase-shifting interferometry. Each femoral head was
8 measured five times on different parts of the surface, with each evaluated area set to 0.4 x 0.55
9 mm. The mean surfaces roughness of the femoral heads was as follows (mean \pm standard
10 deviation): 7.19 ± 0.62 nm for CoCrMo, 11.46 ± 2.33 nm for FeNiCr, 34.21 ± 4.59 nm for
11 Ti6Al4V and 50.10 ± 15.44 nm for Ti6Al4V + DLC. Fig. 2 (middle and right column) illustrates
12 typical greyscale images of the surface and surface roughness measurements for each femoral
13 head.

1
2 **Fig. 2** 3D scan, surface image and typical surface roughness measurements results for femoral heads made from: a) CoCrMo,
3 b) FeNiCr, c) Ti6Al4V, d) Ti6Al4V + DLC

4 Lastly, the wettability of the femoral heads was characterized using the sessile drop
5 technique, whereby the contact angle between the femoral head surface and a drop of model SF
6 (described subsequently) was measured. The results are presented in Fig. 3.

7
8 **Fig. 3** Contact angles for femoral heads measured with model SF: a) CoCrMo, b) FeNiCr, c) Ti6Al4V, d) Ti6Al4V + DLC

1 As counter-surfaces to the femoral heads, UHMWPE, PMMA, and BK7 glass
 2 acetabular cups were used. The UHMWPE cup was selected for analysis of friction in realistic
 3 material combinations, while the PMMA and BK7 cups were necessary for in-situ observation
 4 of the contact area using fluorescence microscopy and optical interferometry. As with the
 5 femoral heads, the acetabular cups were scanned with a 3D scanner to measure the nominal
 6 diameter of the spherical surface, and an optical profilometer was used to analyse surface
 7 roughness. The results are presented in Tab. 1.

8 **Tab. 1 Characteristics of acetabular cups**

Material	Experiment	Diameter (mm)	Diametric clearance (μm)	Surface roughness (Sa) [nm]
UHMWPE	COF measurement	28.22	240	2709 ± 140
PMMA	In-situ observation by fluorescent microscopy	28.11	130	15.6 ± 0.44
BK7 glass	In-situ observation by optical interferometry	28.05	70	3.6 ± 0.09

9
 10 As a lubricant, model SF was prepared in accordance with methodology outlined by
 11 Galandaková et al. [30]. PBS was used as the basic solution, with the following additions:
 12 bovine serum albumin (BSA, Sigma Aldrich A7030, St. Louis, MO, USA), γ -globulin from
 13 bovine blood (BSG, Sigma Aldrich G5009, St. Louis, MO, USA), hyaluronic acid (HySilk,
 14 Contipro, Dolní Dobrouč, Czechia) and L- α -phosphatidylcholine (Sigma Aldrich P3782, St.
 15 Louis, MO, USA). The concentrations reflected those found in the SF of healthy individuals,
 16 specifically: albumin 20 mg/ml, γ -globulin 3.6 mg/ml, HA 2.5 mg/ml and phospholipids 0.15
 17 mg/ml. For the purpose of measurements using the fluorescent microscope, the individual
 18 components of the model SF were labelled with fluorescent dyes. Albumin was labelled with
 19 Rhodamine B isothiocyanate (RBITC, Sigma Aldrich 283924, St. Louis, MO, USA), while γ -
 20 globulin and hyaluronic acid were labelled with fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC, Sigma
 21 Aldrich F7250, St. Louis, MO, USA).

2.3. Test conditions and results evaluation

All tests were conducted under fully flooded conditions using model SF. The temperature of the contact bodies was maintained at 37° throughout the measurements. A load of 532 N was applied by dead weight on the contact bodies, resulting in varying contact pressure values depending on the material of the ball and cup. The exact contact pressure values for each material combination were determined through the application of Hertzian theory and are presented in Tab. 2.

Tab. 2 Values of contact pressures

Material	BK7 glass cup contact pressure (MPa)	PMMA cup contact pressure (MPa)	UHMPE cup contact pressure (MPa)
CoCrMo	24.1	5.1	2.4
FeNiCr	-	5.1	2.4
Ti6Al4V	21.1	5.1	2.4
Ti6Al4V + DLC	-	5.1	2.4

Firstly, the COF between femoral heads and the UHMWPE cup was measured through the implementation of the following methodology: the pendulum frame was meticulously deflected by 16° and subsequently released, thereby enabling spontaneous damped oscillatory motion to occur. The angular velocity of the pendulum arm was monitored using an accelerometer. The measurement was repeated 10 times conclusively without unloading the contact. The data were processed using MATLAB software (MathWorks, Inc., CA, USA), with the peaks of the angular velocity fitted with a linear function as described in a study by Crisco et al. [31], and the COF values calculated.

In order to simulate the standing and walking phases of the gait cycle, a combined kinematics approach was employed for both fluorescence microscopy and optical interferometry (Fig. 4). The initial phase entailed the cyclic loading and unloading of the static contact. A total of ten cycles were performed, comprising a ten-second loaded phase and a

1 twenty-second unloaded phase. Subsequently, a 60-second relaxation period was conducted
2 under loaded conditions. In the second phase, the pendulum arm was deflected by 16° and
3 released to initiate spontaneous damped oscillation, as was done during the frictional
4 measurements. The third phase comprised maintaining the contact under static loaded
5 conditions for a further 300 seconds, allowing for the observation of the relaxation of the
6 lubricant film.

7 The film thickness values were evaluated from the optical interferometry images and
8 videos, while the fluorescent intensity values were measured from the fluorescence microscopy
9 videos and images. Fluorescent intensity values were normalized in order to account for
10 variations in the initial settings of the light source, microscope filters and used fluorescent
11 markers, which can influence the initial fluorescent intensity. In order to ensure comparability
12 across experiments, the initial fluorescent intensity was set to 1 000 by dividing the starting
13 value by a constant, after which all subsequent data from the experiment were divided by this
14 constant. This normalization method has been previously used and validated in our earlier study
15 [17].

16
17 **Fig. 4** Kinematic conditions of the tests

18 **3. RESULTS**

19 **3.1. Friction**

20 Fig. 5 shows the results of the COF measurements performed between the four
21 investigated femoral heads and the UHMWPE acetabular cup. The COF values reported for
22 three of the four tested femoral heads (CoCrMo, FeNiCr and Ti6Al4V) were found to be highly
23 similar. No discernible trend was identified in the COF measurement outcomes for CoCrMo

1 and FeNiCr. In contrast, a slight increase in COF values from 0.047 to 0.058 was observed for
 2 Ti6Al4V during the initial five measurements, followed by a period of steady-state values
 3 during the remainder of the measurement. Furthermore, the CoCrMo and Ti6Al4V exhibited
 4 identical average COF values following ten consecutive measurements, with a value of 0.056.
 5 The FeNiCr exhibited the lowest average COF, at 0.048 ± 0.004 . Conversely, the Ti6Al4V head
 6 coated with a DLC layer exhibited COF values that were over twice as high as those of the
 7 other specimens, with an average of 0.137 ± 0.002 . The results of individual measurements
 8 reported an initial increase in COF from 0.132 to 0.137, after which the COF values were
 9 stabilized.

10 **Fig. 5** COF between the tested femoral heads and UHMWPE cup: results of individual experiments with each metal femoral
 11 head (left), mean values and standard deviations for each femoral head material (right)

12 To compare a realistic material combination (metal femoral head and UHMWPE cup) and a hip
 13 joint replacement model used for in-situ studies of lubricant film formation, frictional
 14 measurements between all four metal femoral heads and PMMA cup, which was lately used for
 15 measurement with fluorescent microscopy, were conducted. The results of these measurement
 16 are shown in Fig. 6. In comparison with UHMWPE, PMMA exhibited a COF value that was
 17 multiple times higher. The lowest average value of COF was observed once more for the
 18 FeNiCr, with a value of 0.214 ± 0.014 . The results of the individual measurements demonstrated
 19

1 a slight increase in COF from 0.217 to 0.238 during the initial three measurements, followed
 2 by a gradual decrease to 0.189 during the remaining measurements. The CoCrMo exhibited an
 3 average COF value of 0.244 ± 0.011 . With the exception of the initial measurement, the results
 4 of the individual measurements exhibited minimal variation, with a slight increase from 0.234
 5 to 0.255 observed during the final five measurements. In contrast with the findings for the
 6 UHMWPE cup, the impact of the DLC coating on the friction of the 3D printed Ti6Al4V was
 7 reversed. The 3D printed Ti6Al4V femoral head with DLC coating exhibited results that were
 8 more closely aligned with those of the conventionally manufactured specimens (CoCrMo,
 9 FeNiCr) than the Ti6Al4V head without DLC coating, with an average COF value of $0.265 \pm$
 10 0.016 . The individual measurements demonstrated a notable decline in COF from 0.299 to
 11 0.240, during the initial four measurements. This was followed by an increase to 0.274 during
 12 the remaining measurements. The highest average value of COF was observed for the 3D
 13 printed Ti6Al4V specimen without DLC coating, with an average of 0.354 ± 0.013 . The results
 14 demonstrated a gradual increase from 0.327 to 0.376 in the initial seven measurements,
 15 followed by a decrease to 0.355 in the remaining measurements.

16
 17 **Fig. 6** COF between the tested femoral heads and PMMA cup: results of individual experiments with each metal femoral head
 18 (left), mean values and standard deviations for each femoral head material (right)

1 **3.2. Observation of individual SF constituents**

2 The first series of in-situ measurements was focused on the role of individual SF
3 constituents in lubricant film formation. A fluorescence microscope was attached to the
4 pendulum hip joint simulator and albumin, γ -globulin and HA were sequentially labelled with
5 a fluorescent dye. Fig. 7 shows the results of the measurements with SF containing fluorescently
6 labelled albumin, with the fluorescent intensity (dimensionless film thickness) as a function of
7 time. During the first phase of the experiment, which consisted of cyclic loading and unloading
8 of the static contact, the fluorescent intensity increased for all four femoral heads, caused by
9 the formation of a boundary adsorbed film composed of albumin, as can be seen from the
10 images of the contact area taken during the experiments. The initial fluorescent intensity value
11 has been normalized and is therefore the same for all femoral heads. The steepest increase in
12 fluorescent intensity during static loading was reported for Ti6Al4V and the least steep increase
13 was reported for Ti6Al4V with DLC coating. The fluorescent intensity values for individual
14 femoral heads at the end of static loading were as follows: 1639 for Ti6Al4V, 1587 for FeNiCr,
15 1,412 for CoCrMo and 1,233 for Ti6Al4V + DLC.

16 Involvement of the swinging motion resulted in an increase in albumin fluorescent
17 intensity except for CoCrMo, which may have been caused by the damage to the adsorbed
18 protein layer during extension of the pendulum frame. Individual femoral heads then showed
19 different trends in fluorescent intensity during the pendulum swinging motion. Overall, the
20 lowest fluorescent intensity was reported for CoCrMo, while fluorescent intensity gradually
21 increased during the first half of the measurement and then stabilized for the remainder of the
22 measurement. At the end of swinging motion, the fluorescent intensity for CoCrMo was 1,509.
23 The second lowest fluorescent intensity values were measured for Ti6Al4V, while the
24 progression was almost constant, with fluorescent intensity values fluctuating between 1684
25 and 1,724. FeNiCr showed an initial increase of fluorescent intensity during the first few

1 seconds, followed by a slight decrease. At the end of swinging motion, fluorescent intensity for
 2 FeNiCr was 1,808. The swinging motion of FeNiCr also lasted the longest, leading to the lowest
 3 COF between this femoral head and the PMMA acetabular cup. The highest values of
 4 fluorescent intensity, 2,584 at the end, were reported for Ti6Al4V, while the data show a large
 5 fluctuation, probably caused by protein agglomerates entering and leaving the contact area
 6 during the swinging motion. The final stage of the experiment, focusing on albumin boundary
 7 layer relaxation, showed a decrease in fluorescent intensity for CoCrMo, FeNiCr and Ti6Al4V
 8 + DLC femoral head and an increase for Ti6Al4V. At the end of the measurement, the
 9 fluorescent intensity values were (from highest to lowest) – 3,101 for Ti6Al4V, 1,648 for
 10 FeNiCr, 1,554 for Ti6Al4V + DLC and 1,464 for CoCrMo.

11
 12 **Fig. 7** Time-dependent development of fluorescent intensity for all four tested femoral heads during measurements with SF
 13 containing fluorescently labelled albumin (top), images of the contact area taken during the experiments (bottom)

14 The second set of measurements was performed with SF containing fluorescently
 15 labelled γ -globulin. The results in Fig. 8 show that this time FeNiCr achieved the highest

1 fluorescent intensity values at the end of the static loading/unloading phase – 1,145. As in the
2 case of the albumin measurements, FeNiCr was followed by a CoCrMo and Ti6Al4V + DLC
3 with fluorescent intensity values of 1,077 and 1,040 respectively. Contrary to the result with
4 albumin, Ti6Al4V showed the lowest fluorescent intensity value at the end of the static loading
5 phase. The fluorescent intensity increased initially, but at the end of the static loading it was
6 almost the same as at the beginning of the test, indicating that γ -globulin was not part of the
7 adsorbed protein layer or that no boundary lubricating layer was formed.

8 During the second phase, when the pendulum was swinging, Ti6Al4V reported the
9 steepest increase in fluorescent intensity and at the end of this phase it reported the highest
10 value of fluorescent intensity of all the femoral heads tested – 1,260. Ti6Al4V + DLC showed
11 moreless constant values of fluorescent intensity, fluctuating between 1,004 and 1,031, as in
12 the case of measurements with fluorescently labelled albumin. Both conventionally
13 manufactured femoral heads - CoCrMo and FeNiCr - showed a slight decrease in fluorescent
14 intensity. The final relaxation part resulted in a gradual decrease in fluorescent intensity for all
15 femoral heads tested. At the end of the measurement the fluorescent intensity was 1,179 for
16 Ti6Al4V, 990 for Ti6Al4V + DLC, 986 for FeNiCr and 934 for CoCrMo.

2 **Fig. 8** Time-dependent development of fluorescent intensity for all four tested femoral heads during measurements with SF
 3 containing fluorescently labelled γ -globulin, images of the contact area taken during the experiments (bottom)

4 The final set of in-situ fluorescent microscopy observations was made with SF
 5 containing labelled HA. The results in Fig. 9 showed a gradual increase in fluorescent intensity
 6 for all femoral heads as in the case of albumin. However, this time only a slight increase was
 7 observed, which was almost identical for all femoral heads. At the end of static loading, the
 8 fluorescent intensity for individual femoral heads was between 1,038 and 1,095, with the
 9 highest value measured for CoCrMo and the lowest for Ti6Al4V + DLC. During the pendulum
 10 swinging motion, the fluorescent intensity did not change significantly for most samples.
 11 CoCrMo and Ti6Al4V + DLC showed an almost constant progress with quite similar
 12 fluorescent intensity values. For CoCrMo, the fluorescent intensity fluctuated between 1,051
 13 and 1,093 and for Ti6Al4V + DLC between 1,033 and 1,092. The only femoral head that
 14 showed an increase in HA fluorescent intensity during swinging motion was Ti6Al4V. The
 15 fluorescent intensity increased from 1,093 to 1,183. The damped swinging motion between the

1 Ti6Al4V femoral head and PMMA cup also lasted the shortest time, elicited the highest COF
 2 in the contact during motion. The longest swinging motion, i.e. the lowest COF in contact, was
 3 reported for FeNiCr. FeNiCr also reported a decrease in HA fluorescent intensity from 1,141 to
 4 1,085. The final relaxation phase again resulted in a decrease in fluorescent intensity for all
 5 femoral heads tested. The most significant decrease was observed for Ti6Al4V, which reduced
 6 the increase in fluorescent intensity during the swinging motion and approached the final
 7 fluorescent intensity value closer to the rest of the femoral heads tested. The final fluorescent
 8 intensity values were quite close for all femoral heads – 1,014 for Ti6AL4V + DLC, 1,010 for
 9 Ti6Al4V, 993 for FeNiCr and 963 for CoCrMo.

10
 11 **Fig. 9** Time-dependent development of fluorescent intensity for all four tested femoral heads during measurements with SF
 12 containing fluorescently labelled HA, images of the contact area taken during the experiments (bottom)

13 3.3. Film thickness measurements

14 In order to obtain information regarding the film thickness between the femoral head
 15 and acetabular cup contact, the fluorescent microscope was replaced with an optical

1 interferometry apparatus (Fig. 1). Additionally, the PMMA cup was replaced with a BK7 glass
2 acetabular cup that had been coated with an anti-reflex and chromium layer. The same
3 measurement methodology, consisting of static loading, dynamic swinging part and lubricant
4 film relaxation phase, was applied. In this investigation, only CoCrMo femoral head, which is
5 the most commonly used conventionally produced metal femoral head, and the Ti6Al4V
6 femoral head, which is representative of the emerging generation of 3D printed femoral heads,
7 were tested. The results are presented in Fig. 10. As with the observation of contact by
8 fluorescent microscopy, the cyclic loading and unloading of the static contact resulted in the
9 formation of an adsorbed boundary layer and a gradual increase in the film thickness for both
10 femoral heads. Following 10 cycles, the film thickness was observed to be 89 nm for the
11 Ti6Al4V femoral head. CoCrMo femoral head exhibited film thicknesses of 54 nm. During the
12 swinging phase, a notable increase in film thickness was observed in comparison to the static
13 loading and unloading cycles for both the CoCrMo and Ti6Al4V. However, the evolution of
14 the lubricant film thickness for both femoral heads exhibited notable differences. While the
15 CoCrMo exhibited a gradual loss of lubricating film thickness during the swinging motion, the
16 Ti6Al4V initially demonstrated a steep increase in film thickness, followed by a decrease when
17 the motion slowed. Furthermore, the extent of change in thickness was found to vary
18 considerably between these two samples. In the case of CoCrMo, the film thickness exhibited
19 a gradual decrease from 138 to 73 nm. In contrast, Ti6Al4V initially displayed an increase from
20 252 nm up to 467 nm, followed by a subsequent decrease to 287 nm. Furthermore, it can be
21 observed that the movement ceased much earlier for Ti6Al4V, at 14 cycles compared to 50 for
22 the CoCrMo. This is associated with the elevated COF in the contact. In the final phase of the
23 experiment, where the adsorbed boundary layer was maintained under static loading, only a
24 slight reduction in film thickness was evident for both CoCrMo and Ti6Al4V.

1
2 **Fig. 10** Time-dependent development of film thickness for CoCrMo and Ti6Al4V femoral heads (top), chromatic
3 interferograms taken during the experiments (bottom)

4 **4. DISCUSSION**

5 **4.1. General discussion**

6 The present study offers insight into the frictional behaviour and lubricant film
7 formation of 3D printed Ti6Al4V THR femoral heads using a pendulum hip joint simulator,
8 which enables measurements in a realistic ball-in-cup configuration. The results were then
9 compared with CM produced femoral head made from CoCrMo alloy and FeNiCr stainless
10 steel. The frictional measurements comprised 10 repetitions of damped oscillatory motions, and
11 in the majority of cases, the data exhibited high levels of reproducibility. The results for the
12 CoCrMo and FeNiCr femoral heads were found to be close together for both the UHMWPE
13 and PMMA acetabular cups. This is primarily attributable to their same diameter of 27.98 mm,
14 resulting in a same value of diametric clearance [32], comparable surface roughness [33] and
15 wettability [34]. Similarly, Ti6Al4V+DLC exhibited markedly elevated friction caused by
16 higher surface roughness and a lower value of contact angle (Fig. 3). The surface images of
17 Ti6Al4V+DLC (Fig. 2d) revealed the presence of grooves, which were identified as the result

1 of imperfections in the 3D printing or surface finishing process. These grooves (thus textures)
2 have the potential to function as reservoirs for lubricants, to offer space for accumulated wear
3 debris, to function as micro-hydrodynamic bearings, or to reduce the contact area, thereby
4 improving friction and wear rate [35]. A number of studies have demonstrated the beneficial
5 impact of surface grooves on THR friction [36], [37] while some studies [38] have also
6 indicated that micro dimples do not significantly impact the friction performance of THR
7 resembling the importance of the grooves parameters such as shape, size and their distribution
8 on the femoral head surface. The wettability of surfaces, as characterized by contact angle
9 measurements (Fig. 3), influences the absorption of proteins on contact surfaces, which in turn
10 affects friction. Proteins adsorption is more prevalent on hydrophobic surfaces [39], while
11 highly hydrophilic surface of Ti6Al4V+DLC results in limited protein adsorption, preventing
12 the formation of a boundary protective layer.

13 In general, the COF values for the PMMA cup were higher than those for the
14 UHMWPE. PMMA is an amorphous thermoplastic material that is renowned for its perfect
15 optical clarity but often reports high COF, and thus is frequently reinforced or modified with
16 polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) [40], [41] or UHMWPE [42] in order to enhance its tribological
17 properties. Conversely, UHMWPE is a linear polymer with a high molecular weight
18 characterized by excellent wear resistance, low friction and high impact strength [43].
19 Furthermore, PMMA has higher elastic modulus, which results in a smaller contact area and
20 higher contact pressure. This, in turn, may hinder the entry of proteins into contact area,
21 potentially influencing protein adsorption. Furthermore, the disparities in surface roughness and
22 diametric clearance between the PMMA and UHMWPE cups should be considered. A
23 reduction in diametric clearance results in the formation of a thicker lubricant film in contact
24 [15]. Additionally, the effect of DLC coating on Ti6Al4V friction has been observed to differ
25 between PMMA and UHMWPE acetabular cups. In the case of UHMWPE, the harder and

1 rougher surface of DLC may penetrate deeper into the softer and rougher surface of UHMWPE,
2 leading to an adhesion or abrasive wear of the cup. In contrast, penetration of DLC coated
3 surface into the harder PMMA is less pronounced, and the friction of the rougher DLC coated
4 surface is overcome by the uncoated Ti6Al4V, which is known to possess insufficient
5 tribological properties [44].

6 The behaviour of DLC coatings applied to metal components in contact with
7 polyethylene was described in a study by Rothhammer et al. [27], in which it was demonstrated
8 that there was an increase in the coefficient of friction after application of DLC compared to
9 tests where a pure alloy was used. This is in agreement with the results obtained in this study
10 (see Fig. 5), the authors attributed this to the effect of the increase in roughness after DLC
11 application, which was also observed for the specimens tested in this study. In particular, the
12 roughness of the femoral heads increased from about 34 to 50 nm after coating by DLC on
13 Ti6Al4V substrate. Ranuša et al. [45] conducted a study in which they examined samples of
14 cobalt and titanium alloy, produced by AM, with the application of DLC coating. Glass was
15 utilised as a counterpart for the experiments, which, due to more similar properties (such as
16 very low surface roughness and higher modulus of elasticity), can be used for PMMA closures.
17 The results obtained from their study indicated that, during the initial phase of the experiment,
18 the COF levels of the AM Ti6Al4V+DLC samples were notably lower compared to those of
19 the CoCrMo samples. However, after a certain period, a stabilisation was observed, and the
20 friction values became almost equal, which is consistent with the results (see Fig. 6), where the
21 average COF for CoCrMo is 0.244 and for Ti6Al4V+DLC is 0.265.

22 The present study also highlights the role of fluorescence microscopy in elucidating the
23 dynamics of lubricant film formation in hip replacements. The ability to directly visualize
24 individual SF constituents under near-physiological conditions provides critical insights into
25 the adsorption and film dynamics on the femoral head surface. The results showed that under

1 static loading, the adsorbed albumin layer increases with each following cycle (Fig. 7), which
2 is crucial for the formation of a boundary layer protecting the rubbing surfaces [10], enabling
3 further development of the lubricant film under dynamic swinging [15]. Concerning albumin
4 adsorption, the fluorescent images revealed faster initial adsorption onto 3D printed Ti6Al4V.
5 However, the effect was diminished when the 3D printed Ti6Al4V was further coated by DLC.
6 The explanation is likely in the protein conformational changes [46] and significant differences
7 in surface wettability reported above. In particular, it was found that denatured proteins rather
8 adsorb onto hydrophobic surfaces [39]. Thus, it is suggested that the native α -helix structure of
9 albumin tends to be denatured under static loading, leading to the enhancement of adsorbed
10 film on hydrophobic surfaces. The results from the dynamic part of the experiment highlight
11 the importance of the initial adsorbed film since the dynamic film thickness is the highest for
12 the Ti6Al4V head. The up and down fluctuations are attributed to the repeated passage of
13 protein clusters through the contact during changing the motion direction [11].

14 Concerning the second observed protein, γ -globulin, the static part of the test revealed
15 different film behaviour. As shown in Fig. 8, the adsorbed layer is somewhat stable for most
16 heads except for FeNiCr, where the adsorbed layer thickness increases. This might be due to
17 the optimal combination of surface wettability and surface roughness properties. Even though,
18 it must be emphasized that there might be a contribution of chemical composition, as the
19 aforementioned properties do not significantly differ from CoCrMo and Ti6AL4V heads. Thus,
20 a spectroscopic analysis might better reveal the adsorption mechanisms of γ -globulin,
21 motivating future research. The swinging part of the test showed that the film is rather constant
22 or slightly decreases for CoCrMo, FeNiCr and Ti6Al4V + DLC heads, while an increase is
23 observed for Ti6Al4V. Therefore, there is a close link to protein form, as γ -globulin is of β -
24 sheet structure in a native form [46], and it was also observed before that its ability to form a
25 stable lubricating film under motion is a bit limited [4], [18].

1 The last set of fluorescent observations was performed with stained HA. In this case,
2 the variance in results was the least apparent out of the investigated constituents. Under the
3 static test, there is a slight increase in adsorbed HA film (Fig. 9); however, it is not as significant
4 as in the case of albumin and moreless comparable to the results of γ -globulin. Similar
5 behaviour of all the tested heads regarding the formation of HA film is also identified during
6 the swinging motion, where the only worth-mentioning difference may be seen for Ti6Al4V.

7 To sum up, it should be highlighted that pure Ti6Al4V has a very positive impact on
8 lubricant film formation. However, concerning the expected elevated wear of Ti6Al4V under
9 rubbing conditions [47], additional coating with DLC seems necessary. Thus, the overall
10 biotribological performance is in finding the optimal balance between lubrication and
11 associated wear performance. Therefore, long-term wear tests are planned as the next step when
12 assessing the potential involvement of additively manufactured implants in a broader use. While
13 additive manufacturing offers unique customization and surface engineering opportunities, the
14 findings also reveal challenges. The irregularities inherent to the process, such as localized
15 asperities, can disrupt lubricant film formation, leading to adverse wear mechanisms. These
16 challenges emphasize the importance of optimizing post-processing techniques to minimize
17 surface imperfections.

18 **4.2. Limitations**

19 The authors realize that the present study lacks several limitations. First of all, it must
20 be emphasized that the experiments were carried out under a static load of 532 N, while under
21 various daily activities, the load of the joints differs considerably during the cycle. However, it
22 must be noted that the pendulum simulator does not allow control of the load during operation,
23 as the dead weight causes the vertical load. The main benefit of this approach is that it considers
24 realistic conformal conditions, which are found to be more critical than load variance [14].

1 Further concern might be related to limited statistical evidence. In this regard, it is worth
2 mentioning that the cups for testing are costly, and multiple repetitions of a wide range of
3 measurements are simply impossible. However, the authors gained significant experience with
4 these tests before [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [48] and established very strict experimental
5 protocols which must be followed to come up with reliable data. When there is doubt about the
6 experiment's progress, sample quality or any inconsistency in data evaluation, the experiment
7 is excluded from the data set and is repeated with new samples under given conditions.

8 Another limitation might also be identified in the reversed arrangement of the hip joint
9 model, where the head is placed at the top. However, this is the only option that enables (i)
10 friction monitoring due to natural damping of the pendulum arm and (ii) simultaneous in-situ
11 contact observation using optical methods under fully flooded conditions. If the joint
12 arrangement were in a physiological setup (cup on top), the whole couple would have to be
13 covered by some sleeve to avoid fluid leakage, which would disable contact observation. It is
14 nevertheless believed that this experimental limitation should not cause significant
15 discrepancies, as the joint in the body is encapsulated, and the synovial fluid fills the whole
16 joint gap; thus, the contact also operates under a fully flooded regime.

17 Next, the variance in cup materials should be discussed briefly. As mentioned above,
18 the present study employed UHMWPE, PMMA and glass acetabular cups. The motivation for
19 using three different materials is in the abilities of the applied techniques and the intention to
20 come up with reliable, clinically relevant data. UHMWPE is a typical representative of cups
21 used dominantly in practice; it was, therefore, used to assess the frictional performance of the
22 tested cups. However, it is not transparent, so direct contact imaging is not possible. For that
23 reason, the original cup was substituted by PMMA for fluorescence imaging, as PMMA is
24 identified as a soft-matter material with mechanical properties close to the UHMWPE with

1 sufficient optical transparency [17], [49]. The optical glass was then used due to the limitations
2 of optical interferometry described in the below paragraph.

3 Last but not least, it needs to be highlighted that the comprehensive fluorescent
4 observations resulted in a qualitative assessment of the lubricant film thickness. The literature
5 showed that there is a linear dependence between the fluorescent intensity and film thickness;
6 therefore, the higher intensity, the proportionally thicker lubricating film [50], [51]. Apparently,
7 the authors were also quite interested in a quantitative assessment of film thickness. For this
8 purpose, optical interferometry was previously successfully adopted [14], [18]. The biggest
9 limitation is that the counterface must be made from glass (or sapphire) and additionally coated
10 with a thin chromium layer to enhance interference of fringes and allow precise film thickness
11 evaluation. Following previous experience, the authors performed the film thickness
12 measurements, as can be seen in Fig. 10. In contrast to the fluorescent measurement, film
13 thickness was analysed only for the CoCrMo and Ti6Al4V femoral heads. In order to reduce
14 the quantity of glass acetabular cups required for the experiments, measurements with FeNiCr
15 and Ti6Al4V+DLC were not conducted. Especially in the case of Ti6Al4V+DLC, it was
16 anticipated that delamination of the chromium layer and scratching of the glass surface would
17 occur due to the rough and hard surface of the femoral head. It should be noted that the primary
18 objective was to undertake an analysis of conventionally and additively manufactured femoral
19 heads, which was still achieved for CoCrMo and uncoated Ti6Al4V. Nevertheless, some
20 interesting findings are still coming from this analysis, specifically in terms of pretty good film
21 formation ability in the case of the Ti6Al4V head, which is in good compliance with fluorescent
22 observations. Titanium head formed even thicker films than commercial CoCrMo, which was
23 found to be very film-supportive in our previous research [15]. The authors conclude that the
24 data from optical interferometry have rather a supportive character and do not represent the

1 most reliable findings of the present study. For better film thickness assessment in a quantitative
2 way, another measurement technique would have to be adopted.

3 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

4 In conclusion, this study has identified several key findings regarding the surface
5 properties, friction, and lubricant film formation of additively manufactured THRs from
6 Ti6Al4V alloy. A pendulum hip joint simulator, in conjunction with fluorescent microscopy
7 and optical interferometry apparatus, was utilized to analyse COF and film thickness in a
8 realistic ball-in-cup configuration, while the results of 3D printed femoral heads were compared
9 with those of conventionally manufactured femoral heads. The main conclusions are presented
10 below:

- 11 • The additively manufactured Ti6Al4V head showed better protein adsorption and a
12 faster increase in lubricant film thickness, which could potentially contribute to a
13 reduction in contact surface wear. However, concerning the expected elevated wear of
14 Ti6Al4V, an additional surface coating seems to be necessary.
- 15 • Additive manufacturing enables the creation of surfaces with specific imperfection
16 such as uneven surfaces or the presence of pores or dents. These imperfections can
17 enhance the formation of the lubricant film and, subsequently, reduce friction or wear
18 in the THR. Nevertheless, the beneficial impact of these features has not been
19 definitively established.
- 20 • Despite exhibiting higher surface roughness, the friction of additively manufactured
21 femoral heads was found to be comparable to that of conventionally manufactured
22 femoral heads.
- 23 • The application of DLC coating did not result in a smoother surface of the femoral
24 head, likely due to uneven adhesion and existing surface irregularities. The application

1 of DLC coating also resulted in an increase in friction and a reduction in protein and
2 HA adsorption under certain conditions.

3 Additive manufacturing, one of the most promising and advanced technologies of the
4 past few decades, has become a significant part of the orthopaedical implant industry, offering
5 undeniable benefits, while also presenting specific aspects related to the process. Surface
6 imperfections, such as pores or dents, have the potential to affect the longevity and performance
7 of the implant. Therefore, unintentional as well as intentional surface texturing of 3D printed
8 femoral heads should be further investigated. These surface imperfections, particularly in the
9 case of Ti6Al4V alloy, are also associated with a need for better surface finishing techniques,
10 which would result in the creation of smoother rubbing surfaces. The application of DLC
11 coating appears to be a promising method for enhancing the wear resistance of Ti6Al4V.
12 However, in our case, the application of DLC coating resulted in an increase in surface
13 roughness, higher friction and a worsening of protein adsorption. Therefore, an alternative
14 coating to improve Ti6Al4V wear should be examined as well. Lastly, the tribological
15 properties of titanium alloys could be enhanced by the new generations of additively
16 manufactured titanium alloys, such as Ti-Nb-Ta-Zr or Ti-Mo, Ti-Nb-Zr-Sn, which have been
17 shown to exhibit improved biocompatibility and Young's moduli that are closer to those of
18 human bones.

19 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

20 The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in repository Zenodo
21 at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15235279>.

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4 **CONTRIBUTIONS**

5 DR and MV conceived the idea. DR and MV designed the experiments. DR and SU
6 performed the experiments and analysed the data. DR, LO and DN wrote the original draft of
7 the manuscript. MV administrated the project, secured the funding, and supervised the study.

8 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST**

9 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interest or personal
10 relationship that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

11 **REFERENCES**

- 12 [1] Evans, J.T., Evans, J.P., Walker, R.W., Blom, A.W., Whitehouse, M.R., Sayers, A.: How
13 long does a hip replacement last? A systematic review and meta-analysis of case series
14 and national registry reports with more than 15 years of follow-up. *The Lancet*. **393**,
15 (2019). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31665-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31665-9)
- 16 [2] Linder, R., Müller, H., Grenz-Farenholtz, B., Wagner, C., Stockheim, M., Verheyen, F.:
17 Replacement of endoprosthetic implants within a two years follow-up period: a statutory
18 health insurance routine data analysis. *BMC Musculoskeletal Disord*. **13**, (2012).
19 <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2474-13-223>
- 20 [3] Bayliss, L.E., Culliford, D., Monk, A.P., Glyn-Jones, S., Prieto-Alhambra, D., Judge, A.,
21 Cooper, C., Carr, A.J., Arden, N.K., Beard, D.J., Price, A.J.: The effect of patient age at
22 intervention on risk of implant revision after total replacement of the hip or knee: a
23 population-based cohort study. *The Lancet*. **389**, 1424-1430 (2017).
24 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)30059-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)30059-4)

- 1 [4] Nečas, D., Vrbka, M., Urban, F., Křupka, I., Hartl, M.: The effect of lubricant constituents
2 on lubrication mechanisms in hip joint replacements. *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.* **55**,
3 295-307 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2015.11.006>
- 4 [5] Gallo, J., Goodman, S.B., Konttinen, Y.T., Raska, M.: Particle disease: Biologic
5 mechanisms of periprosthetic osteolysis in total hip arthroplasty. *Innate Immun.* **19**, 213-
6 224 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1753425912451779>
- 7 [6] Cross, M.B., Nam, D., Mayman, D.J.: Ideal Femoral Head Size in Total Hip Arthroplasty
8 Balances Stability and Volumetric Wear. *HSS J. Musculoskeletal J. Hosp. Spec. Surg.* **8**,
9 270-274 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11420-012-9287-7>
- 10 [7] Mavraki, A., Cann, P.M.: Friction and lubricant film thickness measurements on
11 simulated synovial fluids. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng., Part J: J. Eng. Tribol.* **223**, 325-335
12 (2009). <https://doi.org/10.1243/13506501JET580>
- 13 [8] Mavraki, A., Cann, P.M.: Lubricating film thickness measurements with bovine serum.
14 *Tribol. Int.* **44**, 550-556 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2010.07.008>
- 15 [9] Fan, J., Myant, C.W., Underwood, R., Cann, P.M., Hart, A.: Inlet protein aggregation.
16 *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng., Part H: J. Eng. Med.* **225**, 696-709 (2011).
17 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0954411911401306>
- 18 [10] Myant, C., Underwood, R., Fan, J., Cann, P.M.: Lubrication of metal-on-metal hip joints:
19 The effect of protein content and load on film formation and wear. *J. Mech. Behav.*
20 *Biomed. Mater.* **6**, 30-40 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2011.09.008>
- 21 [11] Myant, C.W., Cann, P.: The effect of transient conditions on synovial fluid protein
22 aggregation lubrication. *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.* **34**, 349-357 (2014).
23 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2014.02.005>

- 1 [12] Myant, C., Cann, P.: On the matter of synovial fluid lubrication: Implications for Metal-
2 on-Metal hip tribology. *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.* **34**, 338-348 (2014).
3 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2013.12.016>
- 4 [13] Vrbka, M., Křupka, I., Hartl, M., Návrat, T., Gallo, J., Galandáková, A.: In situ
5 measurements of thin films in bovine serum lubricated contacts using optical
6 interferometry. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng., Part H: J. Eng. Med.* **228**, (2014).
7 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0954411913517498>
- 8 [14] Vrbka, M., Nečas, D., Hartl, M., Křupka, I., Urban, F., Gallo, J.: Visualization of
9 lubricating films between artificial head and cup with respect to real geometry.
10 *Biotribology.* **1-2**, 61-65 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotri.2015.05.002>
- 11 [15] Nečas, D., Vrbka, M., Urban, F., Gallo, J., Křupka, I., Hartl, M.: In situ observation of
12 lubricant film formation in THR considering real conformity: The effect of diameter,
13 clearance and material. *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.* **69**, 66-74 (2017).
14 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2016.12.018>
- 15 [16] Nečas, D., Vrbka, M., Rebenda, D., Gallo, J., Galandáková, A., Wolfová, L., Křupka, I.,
16 Hartl, M.: In situ observation of lubricant film formation in THR considering real
17 conformity: The effect of model synovial fluid composition. *Tribol. Int.* **117**, 206-216
18 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2017.09.001>
- 19 [17] Nečas, D., Vrbka, M., Galandáková, A., Křupka, I., Hartl, M.: On the observation of
20 lubrication mechanisms within hip joint replacements. Part I: Hard-on-soft bearing pairs.
21 *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.* **89**, 237-248 (2019).
22 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2018.09.022>
- 23 [18] Nečas, D., Vrbka, M., Gallo, J., Křupka, I., Hartl, M.: On the observation of lubrication
24 mechanisms within hip joint replacements. Part II: Hard-on-hard bearing pairs. *J. Mech.*

- 1 Behav. Biomed. Mater. **89**, 249-259 (2019).
2 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2018.09.026>
- 3 [19] Narra, S.P., Mittwede, P.N., DeVincent Wolf, S., Urish, K.L.: Additive Manufacturing in
4 Total Joint Arthroplasty. *Orthop. Clin. N. Am.* **50**, 13-20 (2019).
5 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocl.2018.08.009>
- 6 [20] Khal, A.-A., Apostu, D., Schiau, C., Bejinariu, N., Pesenti, S., Jouve, J.-L.: Custom-Made
7 3D-Printed Prosthesis after Resection of a Voluminous Giant Cell Tumour Recurrence in
8 Pelvis. *Diagnostics*. **13**, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics13030485>
- 9 [21] Ran, Q., Yang, W., Hu, Y., Shen, X., Yu, Y., Xiang, Y., Cai, K.: Osteogenesis of 3D
10 printed porous Ti6Al4V implants with different pore sizes. *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed.*
11 *Mater.* **84**, 1-11 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2018.04.010>
- 12 [22] Grosse, S., Haugland, H.K., Lilleng, P., Ellison, P., Hallan, G., Høl, P.J.: Wear particles
13 and ions from cemented and uncemented titanium - based hip prostheses—A histological
14 and chemical analysis of retrieval material. *J. Biom. Mater. Res. Part B.* **103**, 709-717
15 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.b.33243>
- 16 [23] Odehnal, L., Ranuša, M., Vrbka, M., Křupka, I., Hartl, M.: Tribological Behaviour of
17 Ti6Al4V Alloy: An Application in Small Joint Implants. *Tribol. Lett.* **71**, (2023).
18 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11249-023-01795-4>
- 19 [24] Bartolomeu, F., Buciumeanu, M., Pinto, E., Alves, N., Silva, F.S., Carvalho, O., Miranda,
20 G.: Wear behavior of Ti6Al4V biomedical alloys processed by selective laser melting,
21 hot pressing and conventional casting. *Trans. Nonferrous Met. Soc. China.* **27**, 829-838
22 (2017). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-6326\(17\)60060-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-6326(17)60060-8)
- 23 [25] Goyal, V., Verma, G.: Tribological Behavior of Direct Metal Laser Sintering–
24 Manufactured Ti6Al4V Alloy in Different Biofluids for Orthopedic Implants. *J. Tribol.*
25 **146**, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4064506>

- 1 [26] Skjöldebrand, C., Tipper, J.L., Hatto, P., Bryant, M., Hall, R.M., Persson, C.: Current
2 status and future potential of wear-resistant coatings and articulating surfaces for hip and
3 knee implants. *Mater. Today Bio.* **15**, (2022).
4 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtbio.2022.100270>
- 5 [27] Rothhammer, B., Neusser, K., Bartz, M., Wartzack, S., Schubert, A., Marian, M.:
6 Evaluation of the wear-resistance of DLC-coated hard-on-soft pairings for biomedical
7 applications. *Wear.* **523**, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2023.204728>
- 8 [28] Thorwarth, K., Thorwarth, G., Figi, R., Weisse, B., Stiefel, M., Hauert, R.: On Interlayer
9 Stability and High-Cycle Simulator Performance of Diamond-Like Carbon Layers for
10 Articulating Joint Replacements. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **15**, 10527-10540 (2014).
11 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms150610527>
- 12 [29] Oliveira, L.Y.S. de, Siqueira, C.J.M., Fernandes, B.L., Kuromoto, N., Retraint, D.: Wear
13 behavior of Diamond-like Carbon Deposited on Ti6Al4V Prepared with Surface
14 Mechanical Attrition Treatment. *Mater. Res.* **22**, (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-5373-mr-2018-0568>
- 15
16 [30] Galandáková, A., Ulrichová, J., Langová, K., Hanáková, A., Vrbka, M., Hartl, M., Gallo,
17 J.: Characteristics of synovial fluid required for optimization of lubrication fluid for
18 biotribological experiments. *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. Part B: Applied Biomaterials.* **105**,
19 1422-1431 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.b.33663>
- 20 [31] Crisco, J.J., Blume, J., Teeple, E., Fleming, B.C., Jay, G.D.: Assuming exponential decay
21 by incorporating viscous damping improves the prediction of the coefficient of friction in
22 pendulum tests of whole articular joints. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng., Part H: J. Eng. Med.* **221**,
23 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1243/09544119JEIM248>

- 1 [32] Brockett, C.L., Harper, P., Williams, S., Isaac, G.H., Dwyer-Joyce, R.S., Jin, Z., Fisher,
2 J.: *J. Mater. Sci.: Mater. Med.* **19**, 1575-1579 (2008). [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10856-007-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10856-007-3298-9)
3 [3298-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10856-007-3298-9)
- 4 [33] Vrbka, M., Nečas, D., Bartošík, J., Hartl, M., Křupka, I., Galandáková, A., Gallo, J.:
5 Determination of a Friction Coefficient for THA Bearing Couples. *Acta chirurgiae*
6 *orthopaedicae et traumatologiae Cechoslovaca.* **82**, 341-347 (2015).
7 <https://doi.org/10.55095/achot2015/057>
- 8 [34] Zhang, C., Fujii, M.: Influence of Wettability and Mechanical Properties on Tribological
9 Performance of DLC Coatings under Water Lubrication. *J. Surf. Eng. Mater. Adv.*
10 *Technol.* **05**, 110-123 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.4236/jsemt.2015.53013>
- 11 [35] Allen, Q., Raeymaekers, B.: Surface Texturing of Prosthetic Hip Implant Bearing
12 Surfaces: A Review. *J. Tribol.* **143**, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4048409>
- 13 [36] Tewelde, F.B., Allen, Q., Zhou, T.: Multiscale Texture Features to Enhance Lubricant
14 Film Thickness for Prosthetic Hip Implant Bearing Surfaces. *Lubricants.* **12**, (2024).
15 <https://doi.org/10.3390/lubricants12060187>
- 16 [37] Nečas, D., Usami, H., Niimi, T., Sawae, Y., Křupka, I., Hartl, M.: Running-in friction of
17 hip joint replacements can be significantly reduced. *Friction.* **8**, 1137-1152 (2020).
18 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40544-019-0351-x>
- 19 [38] Choudhury, D., Ay Ching, H., Mamat, A.B., Cizek, J., Abu Osman, N.A., Vrbka, M.,
20 Hartl, M., Krupka, I.: Fabrication and characterization of DLC coated microdimples on
21 hip prosthesis heads. *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. Part B.* **103**, (2015).
22 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.b.33274>
- 23 [39] Heuberger, M.P., Widmer, M.R., Zobeley, E., Glockshuber, R., Spencer, N.D.: Protein-
24 mediated boundary lubrication in arthroplasty. *Biomaterials.* **26**, 1165-1173 (2005).
25 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2004.05.020>

- 1 [40] Gu, D., Zhang, L., Chen, S., Song, K., Liu, S.: Significant Reduction of the Friction and
2 Wear of PMMA Based Composite by Filling with PTFE. *Polymers*. **10**, (2018).
3 <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym10090966>
- 4 [41] Peng, S., Zhang, L., Xie, G., Guo, Y., Si, L., Luo, J.: Friction and wear behavior of PTFE
5 coatings modified with poly (methyl methacrylate). *Composites, Part B*. **172**, 316-322
6 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2019.04.047>
- 7 [42] Gu, D., Wang, S., Zhang, J., Liu, K., Chen, S., Chen, X., Wang, Z., Liu, J.: Improved
8 Tribological Properties of Poly(methyl methacrylate) Based Composites by the
9 Synergistic Effect of Incorporating Ultra-High Molecular Weight Polyethylene and Heat
10 Treatment. *J. Mater. Eng. Perform.* **31**, (2022). [https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-022-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-022-06638-2)
11 [06638-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-022-06638-2)
- 12 [43] Merola, M., Affatato, S.: Materials for Hip Prostheses: A Review of Wear and Loading
13 Considerations. *Materials*. **12**, (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12030495>
- 14 [44] Philip, J.T., Mathew, J., Kuriachen, B.: Tribology of Ti6Al4V: A review. *Friction*. **7**, 497-
15 536 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40544-019-0338-7>
- 16 [45] Ranuša, M., Čípek, P., Vrbka, M., Paloušek, D., Křupka, I., Hartl, M.: Tribological
17 behaviour of 3D printed materials for small joint implants: A pilot study. *J. Mech. Behav.*
18 *Biomed. Mater.* **132**, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2022.105274>
- 19 [46] Nečas, D., Sawae, Y., Fujisawa, T., Nakashima, K., Morita, T., Yamaguchi, T., Vrbka,
20 M., Křupka, I., Hartl, M.: The Influence of Proteins and Speed on Friction and Adsorption
21 of Metal/UHMWPE Contact Pair. *Biotribology*. **11**, 51-59 (2017).
22 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotri.2017.03.003>
- 23 [47] Katti, K.S., Verma, D., Katti, D.R.: Materials for joint replacement. *Joint Replacement*
24 *Technology*. 81-104 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781845694807.1.81>

- 1 [48] Lu, X., Nečas, D., Meng, Q., Rebenda, D., Vrbka, M., Hartl, M., Jin, Z.: Towards the
2 direct validation of computational lubrication modelling of hip replacements. *Tribol. Int.*
3 **146**, (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2020.106240>
- 4 [49] Nečas, D., Vrbka, M., Marian, M., Rothammer, B., Tremmel, S., Wartzack, S.,
5 Galandáková, A., Gallo, J., Wimmer, M.A., Křupka, I., Hartl, M.: Towards the
6 understanding of lubrication mechanisms in total knee replacements – Part I. *Tribol. Int.*
7 **156**, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2021.106874>
- 8 [50] Azushima, A.: In lubro 3D measurement of oil film thickness at the interface between
9 tool and workpiece in sheet drawing using a fluorescence microscope. *Tribol. Int.* **38**,
10 105-112 (2005). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2004.04.006>
- 11 [51] Azushima, A.: In situ 3D measurement of lubrication behavior at interface between tool
12 and workpiece by direct fluorescence observation technique. *Wear.* **260**, 243-248 (2006).
13 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2005.01.053>